

Using singular value decomposition to adapt Prony's method for signal denoising

T. Schanze^{1*}

¹ Institute for Biomedical Engineering (IBMT), Faculty of Life Science Engineering (LSE), Technische Hochschule Mittelhessen (THM) - University of Applied Sciences, Gießen, Germany

* Corresponding author, email: thomas.schanze@lse.thm.de

Abstract: Prony's method approximates a sequence of data points by a linear superposition of complex exponentials. The computation of the parameters of the complex exponentials by using the Moore-Penrose inverse is extended to the use of singular value decomposition (SVD) in order to obtain a dimension reduction. The application to a noise contaminated electrocardiogram signal shows the potential of the method to approximate signals by sparse spectral representations.

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I. Introduction

Already in 1795, Gaspard de Prony [1, 2] published a clever trick to reconstruct functions from their values at given points, which he invented when solving a problem in physical chemistry. His idea is to solve a non-linear approximation problem, i.e., the approximation of a data sequence by a linear combination of complex exponential functions, by root finding and linear equation solving. His technique was later successfully used in many different fields, especially in the field of spectral signal analysis. In addition, Prony's method is somehow related to the concept of sparsity, what recently came into the focus of attention [3].

It is well known that Prony's method is very powerful to represent noise-free data. Here we focus on an approach that uses Moore-Penrose inverse and show how to modify it by using singular value decomposition (SVD) to denoise signals. The potential of the method, especially with respect to sparse spectral analysis and signal denoising, is shown by using an ECG signal and its artificially noise contaminated copy.

II. Material and methods

II.I. Prony's method

Let x_n be a uniformly sampled signal. With reference to [4] we look at the model of order p given by

$$x_n = -\sum_{k=1}^p A_k e^{i\theta_k} e^{(\alpha_k + i2\pi f_k)(n-1)\Delta t} \quad (1)$$

with $n = 1, \dots, N$, amplitude A_k , phase θ_k , damping factor α_k , frequency f_k , and sampling interval Δt . This equation can be written as

$$x_n = -\sum_{k=1}^p h_k z_k^{n-1} \quad (2)$$

which is a general solution of a homogeneous linear difference equation. If (2) has p different roots, we consider

$$\phi(z) = \prod_{k=1}^p (z - z_k) = \sum_{k=0}^p a_k z^{p-k}, \quad a_0 = 1 \quad (3)$$

where z_k is a Prony or characteristic root.

Equation (3) defines an autoregressive prediction model, which can be used to find the a_k by solving

$$x_{p+d} = -\sum_{k=1}^p a_k x_{p+d-k}, \quad d = 1, \dots, N - p \quad (4)$$

This can be achieved by using the Moore-Penrose pseudo inverse. When all a_k are known, the roots z_k of (3) can be computed. The next step is to calculate damping factors and frequencies:

$$\alpha_k = \frac{\ln|z_k|}{\Delta t}, \quad f_k = \frac{\tan^{-1}(\text{Im}(z_k)/\text{Re}(z_k))}{2\pi\Delta t} \quad (5)$$

Since the roots z_k are known, we can solve (2), e.g. by using the Moore-Penrose inverse. When the h_k are given, we can compute the amplitudes and the phases:

$$A_k = |h_k|, \quad \theta_k = \tan^{-1}(\text{Im}(h_k)/\text{Re}(h_k)) \quad (6)$$

The method produces an efficient or sparse representation of a signal by complex exponentials, which means that a small number of representation parameters, here a small number of Prony parameters subsets ($A_k, \theta_k, \alpha_k, f_k$), can encode a huge number of data points. Since the Prony frequencies are calculated from the data, there are no spectral leakage effects [5] as known from Fourier transform approaches that use predefined fixed Fourier frequencies.

II.II. Extending Prony's method for denoising

An obvious approach for denoising is to use order $p = N/2$, which implies $d = p$, cp. (4). The next step is to zero small Prony components and to use (1) to get a noise reduced signal. Another approach is to select $p < N/2$, and to solve an overdetermined linear system. However, this is useful to reduce the unfavorable influence of noise when estimating Prony parameters. Another approach is to use singular value decomposition (SVD). If we write (4) in matrix style, we obtain

$$\mathbf{x} = -\mathbf{X} \mathbf{a} \quad (7)$$

Using the Moore-Penrose inverse of \mathbf{X} , we get, as stated above, the solution $\mathbf{a} = -\mathbf{X}^\dagger \mathbf{x}$.

If the data are noisy, then \mathbf{X} is somehow contaminated. To reduce noise influence, we calculate the SVD of \mathbf{X} , i.e., $\mathbf{USV}^* = \mathbf{X}$. Note that the diagonal matrix \mathbf{S} contains the singular values, the columns of \mathbf{U} and \mathbf{V} are called left- and right-singular vectors, respectively. It is easy to prove $\mathbf{X}^\dagger = \mathbf{VS}^\dagger \mathbf{U}^*$, where \mathbf{S}^\dagger is formed from \mathbf{S} by taking the reciprocal of each of its non-zero elements.

Since strong signal components are related to large singular values, the influence of broadband noise, which is related to small singular values [6], can be reduced. Setting the components of \mathbf{S} that are small to zero, we get the matrix \mathbf{S}_{red} . The resulting $\mathbf{X}_{\text{red}}^\dagger = \mathbf{VS}_{\text{red}}^\dagger \mathbf{U}^*$ has, compared to \mathbf{X} , reduced rank and can be used to estimate the a_k :

$$\mathbf{a} = -\mathbf{X}_{\text{red}}^\dagger \mathbf{x} \quad (8)$$

Then, as shown above, the Prony parameters can be computed. A simple method for determining the number of singular values to be retained for dimension reduction, is a graphical representation known as a scree plot [6].

To reduce numerical problems respectively to improve the SVD Prony approximation, only those roots z_k are allowed for approximation for which the following applies:

$$1 - \Delta < |z_k| < 1 + \Delta, \text{ e.g. } \Delta = 0.001 \quad (9)$$

III. Results and discussion

In order to test the method, we use a section consisting of $N = 2p = 2000$ samples from an ECG recording and its Gaussian white noise contaminated copy. Figure 1 shows the original signal, the noise contaminated copy, and signals denoised by the introduced SVD Prony denoising method. Equation (9) was applied to increase numerical stability with $\Delta = 0.001$. Note, this denoising method preserves essential signal features, as can be seen in this figure. The best approximation to the original signal shows signal e of Fig. 1. Note that the signal structure is preserved.

To quantify the denoising performance the standard deviation of the difference between the original signal and the denoised noisy signal is calculated. Table 1 shows that the denoising quality depends on the number of the largest singular values used. The best signal recovery or rather denoising was achieved for 50 singular values, as estimated by scree plot. For these values, the number of Prony parameter subsets is 52, indicating an efficient and sparse representation, respectively.

The obtained results indicate that SVD and Prony's method can be advantageously combined to denoise signals. However, for automatic optimal denoising signal driven approaches for estimating appropriate parameters of the method must be developed.

IV. Conclusions

The presented method indicates the potential of combining Prony's method with other methods, e.g., SVD, to create sparse spectral signal representation in combination with denoising.

Figure 1: Prony method-based approximation and denoising of an ECG signal: a) Segment of an ECG recording, b) noisy signal copy, c-f) signals obtained by applying the introduced SVD Prony method to the noisy signal copy. Table 1 provides additional information. The author's ECG was recorded with a Biopac MP36 system under resting conditions. The ECG was sampled at 1 kHz and bandpass filtered.

Table 1: Standard deviation σ of the difference between original signal and denoised signal and number of Prony parameter subsets $\#P$ depend on the number of largest singular values $\#s$.

Fig. 1: signal	b	c	d	e	f
$\#s$	-	200	100	50	20
σ	0.050	0.021	0.020	0.016	0.041
$\#P$	-	94	72	52	26

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